

Effects of thermal residual stress on mechanical properties of the SiC fiber reinforced SiO₂- mullite composites

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SUMMARY: As a potential material for high temperature services, unidirectional SiC fiber reinforced SiO₂- mullite composites were fabricated by slurry impregnation method and liquid phase hot-pressing. A sintered SiC fiber was selected as the reinforcement. The hot-pressing was performed in graphite dies at the conditions of 1923 K, 30 MPa, 3.6 ks in vacuum. In order to investigate influence of thermal residual stress on the mechanical properties, three levels of matrix composition were selected, i.e., SiO₂- 3.7, 30, 50 mol. % Al₂O₃, to control thermo-elastic mismatch between fiber and matrix.

Three-point flexural test was carried out at 298 K and 1573 K. The ultimate strength was nearly 1 GPa at each test temperature except for the SiO₂- 3.7 mol. % Al₂O₃ matrix composite tested at 1573 K. Thus, the effect of thermal residual stress on the ultimate strength was not remarkable. Furthermore, the effect of the thermal residual stress on the proportional limit of the composites was investigated during three-point flexural test with acoustic emission (AE) monitoring at 298 K. The highest proportional limit was resulted from the highest compressive residual stress in the matrix of SiO₂- 3.7 mol. % Al₂O₃ composite. However, no apparent matrix cracking stress was detected by monitoring AE signals during three-point flexural test.

The SiO₂- 3.7 mol. % Al₂O₃ matrix composite with large amount of SiO₂ glass in the matrix caused plastic deformation of the test pieces at 1573 K. On the other hand, the network structure that the primary mullite crystal bonds each other in the SiO₂- 30, 50 mol. % Al₂O₃ matrix composite was effective to prevent the plastic deformation of the matrices during the flexural test at 1573 K.

KEYWORDS: CMC, residual stress, flexural test, acoustic emission (AE), FEA

INTRODUCTION

Silicon carbide (SiC) fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites are being developed as a candidate for toughened thermo-structural materials [1]. Damage tolerant characteristics of ceramic matrix composite (CMC) arise because of stress redistribution mechanism, involving matrix cracking and stochastic fiber failure, accompanied by debonding and sliding interface [2-4]. All of the damage tolerant CMCs have relied on a thin weak interphase between the fiber and the matrix. The interphase used in most commercial products consists of either carbon or boron nitride [5]. Because carbon is sensitive to oxidation at temperature > 773 K [6], covering the carbon interphase with oxide materials can be considered as a candidate for its protection from oxidation. It is introduced that SiO₂ has the lowest oxygen permeability of any oxide [7]. For potential high temperature structure applications, mullite (3Al₂O₃•2SiO₂) has been considered an important ceramic material for its excellent thermal shock resistivity, thermal stability, and high-temperature creep behavior [8,9]. In recent years, a sintered SiC fiber consisted of only beta SiC microcrystalline was developed [10]. The fiber has excellent phase stability and mechanical properties up to 2173 K in argon gas atmosphere. From these backgrounds, we fabricated the sintered SiC fiber with CVD carbon coating reinforced SiO₂-mullite matrix composites.

It is known that thermal residual stress is developed from thermo-elastic mismatch between the fiber and the matrix. The stress often influences strength and interfacial properties of the composites [5,11]. In this study, in order to control the nature of thermal residual stress field between the fiber and the matrix, three levels of matrix compositions (SiO₂- 3.7, 30, 50 mol.

% Al₂O₃) were selected. The purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of thermal residual stress on mechanical properties and fracture behavior of the composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

A sintered SiC fiber “Tyranno SA” tows with average diameter of 7.5 μm from Ube Industry Ltd. was used as the reinforcement. The fibers were coated with 0.8 μm-thick carbon layer by using CVD (Pyrograph, Toyo Tanso Co., Ltd.). Three matrix compositions were selected, i.e. SiO₂- 3.7, 30, 50 mol. % Al₂O₃ shown in the phase diagram (Fig. 1(a)). CTE of the each component is 4.5 ppm for SiC fiber, 0.15 ppm for SiO₂, 5.7 ppm for mullite, respectively. The CTE of the matrix will increase with Al₂O₃ content in the matrix. Both SiO₂ powder (SO-C2, Admatechs Co., Ltd.) and Al₂O₃ powder (AKP-30, Sumitomo Chemical Co., Ltd.) were used as starting materials for the matrices.

Fig. 1 Phase diagram of a SiO₂- Al₂O₃ materials.

Fabrication process

The slurries of three matrix compositions were prepared by dispersing the SiO₂ powder and Al₂O₃ powder into distilled water with planetary a ball-milling machine. The fiber tows were impregnated by the slurry and dried at 343 K for 86.4 ksec. The preforms for composites were hot-pressed at the conditions of 30 MPa for 3.6 ksec at 1923 K in vacuum (10⁻² Pa) and then cooled at the rate of 5 K/ min. Unidirectionally reinforced ceramics matrix composites were obtained with the dimensions of 20 mm (width)× 80 mm (length)× approximately 5 mm (thickness). The longitudinal direction corresponds to the fiber axis direction. The density of each composite was measured by the Archimedes’ principle. The fiber volume fraction in the composites was examined by a commercial image processing system (Image-pro plus ver.4.0). For the observation with scanning electron microscope (SEM), the composites were cut in the plane perpendicular to the fiber axis, which were polished to 1μm diamond paste and etched by 46 % HF solution for 60 sec. In this paper, obtained composites are expressed as follows, SiC_f/ SiO₂- 3.7 mol. % Al₂O₃: 3.7 mol. % composite, SiC_f/ SiO₂- 30 mol. % Al₂O₃: 30 mol. % composite, SiC_f/ SiO₂- 50 mol. % Al₂O₃: 50 mol. % composite, respectively.

Finite element analysis (FEA)

In order to calculate the thermal residual stress developed in the composites during cooling process, FEA was carried out using a commercial software (ANSYS ver.5.7). The properties of the composites constituents used in the analyses are listed in Table 1. Due to symmetry in the geometry and the boundary conditions, the FEA was performed on a half-section of the composites divided by mirror symmetry as shown in Fig. 2. The nodes on the lower section has fixed displacement $u_z = 0$ which is required by symmetry. On the other hand, the nodes on the upper section have uniform displacement ($u_z = \text{free}$). Although the fabricating temperature of the composites was 1973 K, it was assumed that thermal residual stress was developed during cooling process from 1373 K (softening temperature of SiO₂ glass [12]) to 298 K. Fiber volume fraction (V_f) used in the FEA was fixed on 50 %. The node solutions within 6.24 μm from the center of the fiber which is located in the center of the model are examined. On the node solutions in fiber, fiber/ carbon interface, carbon/ matrix interface, and matrix, average stress in “r” and “z” direction were evaluated.

Table 1 Thermoelastic parameters of the the composites.

elements	fiber	graphite			matrix		
		$r (r-\theta)$	$\theta (\theta-z)$	$z (z-r)$	3.7 mol.%	30 mol.%	50 mol.%
mullite V_f (%)					9(2)	53(2)	86(2)
elastic modulus (GPa)		1.4(1)	34.5(1)	34.5(1)			
modulus of transverse elasticity (GPa)	404(1)	1.32(3)	14.9(3)	1.31(3)	51(2)	121(2)	183(2)
Poisson's ratio	0.24(1)	0.012(1)	0.16(1)	0.34(1)	0.18(1)	0.21(1)	0.24(1)
CTE (ppm/ K)	4.5(1)	28(1)	1.7(1)	1.7(1)	1.41(1)	4.13(1)	5.31(1)

(1): quoted, (2): measured, (3): calculated

Fig. 2 Schematic illustrations of (a) the finiteelement model and (b) boundary conditions.

Push-out test

Fiber push-out test was carried out to estimate the shear stress at fiber/ matrix interface. A thin slice (130 μm thickness) was cut perpendicular to the fiber axis and then the surfaces were polished by 1 μm diamond paste. The thin slice was placed on a resilient substrate with a slit (300 μm width), and filaments were individually loaded by the Vickers indenter (MZT-4, Akashi Co.) until the first evidence of filament movement was found. The first evidence of filament motion was detected by load-constant part in the load vs. displacement curve. The curve was generated by measuring the load by a load-cell when the filament was pushed at a constant loading rate of 10 mN/ s up to 150 mN. The interfacial shear stress (τ) is determined by the following equation; $\tau = F / \pi d t$, where F indicates the load at which a filament pushed out, d and t indicate filament diameter and thickness of the specimen, respectively.

Three-point flexural test with acoustic emission (AE) monitoring

Five specimens having dimensions of 4 mm (width) \times 40 mm (length) \times 3 mm (thickness) were prepared for each composite. Flexural test was conducted at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/ min at 298 K and 1573 K. The span length of lower pins was 30 mm. Both universal testing machines Shimadzu Autograph AG-50G for the flexural test at 298 K and Instron1175 for the test at 1573 K were used.

The data of load and strain during the test at 298 K was stored in a computer at the sampling rate of 20 Hz. Stress-strain curve was drawn using the data. Furthermore, moving average " $\Delta\sigma/\Delta\varepsilon$ " corresponding to the proportional ratio was calculated by every $\Delta\varepsilon = 50$.

All flexural tests performed at 298 K were monitored by AE technique. Two sensors (M304A, Fuji Ceramics Co.) having a pre-amplifier (A1002, Fuji Ceramics Co.) were attached to the specimen at each end-plane in the longitudinal direction by using an adhesive agent (Aron alpha, Toagosei Co., Ltd.), and a strain gauge (KFG-2-120-C1-11 L3M2R, Kyowa Electronic Instruments Co., Ltd.) was pasted on the tensile surface (lower surface of the specimen) by using an adhesive agent (CC-33A, Kyowa Electronic Instruments Co., Ltd.) shown in Fig. 3. All the signals detected by the sensors were amplified by the pre-amplifier and then stored and analyzed by using an AE system (Dynamic crack monitor, JT Tohsi inc.) with a software (DCM120 ver.1.31, JT Tohsi inc.). A threshold of 0.062 V was used. After storage, the signals were subjected to a liner location procedure to determine the location of the AE signal source. In the analysis of the AE results, the events in restricted location were used. The location is ± 5 mm from the longitudinal center of the specimen. Individual

amplitude and cumulative number of the AE signals were stored in a computer.

In order to investigate the relationship between stress-strain behavior, AE events and microfractures in the composite structure, optical microscope observation was carried out on the central region of pre-polished tensile surface of the specimens in longitudinal direction relaxed from the loads corresponding to 0.1, 0.25 or 0.5% strain levels.

Fig. 3 Attachment of the AE sensor and the strain gauge to the flexural specimens.

Comparison of the flexural fracture behavior at 298 K and 1573 K

Load-displacement curve was drawn from the data stored during the test to compare the flexural behavior at 298 K and 1573 K.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Density, V_f and microstructure

The density and V_f of the composites were shown in Table 2. Though the density of the composites increased with increasing Al_2O_3 content in the matrix, V_f decreased, contrary. Densification of the preform of 3.7 mol. % composite was larger than that of the 30 or 50 mol. % composites during hot-pressing. This implies that viscosity of the matrices increase with increasing Al_2O_3 content in the matrix. SEM images of the composites polished and etched by HF solution are shown in Fig. 4. Glassy SiO_2 phase was removed by etching. Higher Al_2O_3 content in the matrix causes higher volume fraction of mullite crystals in the matrix. Volume fraction of the primary mullite crystal in each matrix was 9 vol. % for the 3.7 mol. % composite, 53 vol. % for the 30 mol. % composite, 86 vol. % for the 50 mol. % composite, respectively.

Table 2 Density, V_f and interfacial shear stress.

sample name	density (g/cm ³)	V_f (%)	interfacial shear stress (MPa)
SiC_f/SiO_2 - 3.7 mol.% Al_2O_3	2.48	40.0	22.4
SiC_f/SiO_2 - 30 mol.% Al_2O_3	2.63	32.5	24.7
SiC_f/SiO_2 - 50 mol.% Al_2O_3	2.89	25.7	46.5

Fig. 4 SEM images of SiC_f/SiO_2 - mullite composites. (polished surface, glassy SiO_2 was removed).

Finite element analysis (FEA)

Calculated average thermal residual stress is shown in Table 3. Higher fiber cramping (compressive) residual stress is developed in “r” direction at fiber/ carbon interface according to the increase in CTE of the matrix compared to CTE of the fiber. Smaller CTE of the matrix compared to that of the fiber enhances the tendency of interfacial debonding. This will lead to weaker interfacial shear stress.

As increasing in relative thermal expansion ratio of the matrix to the fiber, the compressive stress of the fiber in “z” direction increases. This will enlarge fracture strain of the fiber when

the tensile stress will be applied to the composite. However, in this case, the fracture strain of the matrix will be reduced. When 0.1% strain is applied to the composite addition to the thermal stress, average stress working at the fiber/ carbon interface in “r” direction increase from 54.8 to 64.7 MPa for 3.7 mol. % composite, 22.1 to 32.8 MPa for 30 mol. % composite and -12.8 to -6.4 MPa for 50 mol. % composite. The stress levels in the 3.7 mol. % composite seems to be enough to induce interfacial debonding. Average stress working in the matrix in “z” direction also increases from -149 MPa to 111 MPa for 3.7 mol. % composite, from -35 MPa to 645 MPa for 30 mol. % composite and from 106 MPa to 1218 MPa for 50 mol. % composite. These results will be confirmed by flexural test with AE described as follows.

Table 3 Calculated thermal residual stress in the composites.

sample name	calculated thermal residual stress (MPa)							
	fiber		fiber/ graphite interface		graphite/ matrix interface		matrix	
	dir.		dir.		dir.		dir.	
	r	z	r	z	r	z	r	z
SiC _f / SiO ₂ - 3.7 mol.% Al ₂ O ₃	55.1	255	54.8	94.4	47.1	-10.8	17.7	-149
SiC _f / SiO ₂ - 30 mol.% Al ₂ O ₃	22.8	76.8	22.1	15.2	18.8	-40.9	6.66	-35.0
SiC _f / SiO ₂ - 50 mol.% Al ₂ O ₃	-13.5	-115	-12.8	-114	-14.2	-3.59	-8.53	106

Push-out test

Measured shear stress at fiber/ carbon interface is shown in Table 2. The stress increased with an increase in the Al₂O₃ content in the matrix. This tendency agrees with result of FEA.

Three-point flexural test with acoustic emission (AE) monitoring

Figure 5 shows the evolution of the stress, moving average " $\frac{\Delta\sigma}{\Delta\epsilon}$ ", amplitude of AE and cumulative numbers of AE events versus strain in the tensile surface during the flexural test performed at 298 K. Although ultimate strength of the composites is nearly 1 GPa, both stress-strain curves and AE signals depend on the Al₂O₃ content in the matrix. Figure 6 shows optical microscope images of the central region of pre-polished tensile surface of specimens in longitudinal direction relaxed from the loads correspond to 0.1 or 0.25 or 0.5% strain levels. Circle and arrow marks in the figure indicate matrix crack and fiber failure, respectively.

Figure 5 (a) shows typical result of the test conducted on the 3.7 mol. % composite. Stress increased proportionally with strain up to fracture. The moving average keeps constant at approximately 200 GPa. As to the AE behavior, the rate of events increases from approximately 0.4% strain. The AE signals above 5 V are found over 0.4% strain. As shown in Fig. 6, no damage is found in the tensile surface of the flexural specimens up to 0.25% strain. Fiber failures are observed in the surface relaxed from 0.5% strain. Thus the AE signals above 5 V will be caused by fiber failures.

Figure 5 (b) shows typical result of the test conducted on the 30 mol. % composite. Stress increased proportionally with strain up to 0.3% strain. The rate of events increases from approximately 0.3% strain. The moving average keeps constant at approximately 200 GPa up to 0.3% strain and then decreased gradually to fracture. The AE signals above 5 V are found over 0.3% strain. As shown in Fig. 6, no damage is found in the tensile surface of the flexural specimens up to 0.25% strain, both fiber failures and matrix cracks are observed in the surface relaxed from 0.5% strain. The AE signals above 5 V will be caused by both fiber failures and matrix crackings.

Figure 5 (c) shows typical result of the test conducted on the 50 mol. % composite. Stress increased proportionally with strain up to 0.1% strain. Reduction of the moving average is found at 0.1 ~ 0.3% strain levels. Between 0.3 ~ 0.75% strain levels, the moving average (nearly 100 GPa) showed a good agreement with the value " $E_f \times V_f (= 40 \text{ GPa} \times 26\%)$ ". This means that the matrix cracks are saturated and the stress is conducted by the bridging fibers across the matrix crack. The highest fracture strain level is observed in the 50 mol. % composite compared to the other composites as expected by FEA. As shown in Fig. 5 (c), the strain

levels in which AE signals above 5 V were detected between 0.1 ~ 0.3% strain. In this composite, matrix cracks were already observed in the surface of the specimen relaxed from even 0.25% strain shown in Fig. 6. As expected by FEA, this phenomenon will be caused by matrix cracking. Between 0.25 and 0.5% strain, growth of the matrix crack was not found. Between 0.6 ~ 0.75% strain, gradual reduction of the moving average are found. This will be caused by the stochastic failure of bridging fibers.

Fig. 5 Stress- strain curves with $d\sigma/d\varepsilon$ value and the evolution of the amplitude and the cumulative number of acoustic emission events during flexural testing of the composites.
 (a) $\text{SiC}_f/\text{SiO}_2$ -3.7 mol.% Al_2O_3 , (b) $\text{SiC}_f/\text{SiO}_2$ -30 mol.% Al_2O_3 , (c) $\text{SiC}_f/\text{SiO}_2$ -50 mol.% Al_2O_3

The initial AE signal above 5 V approximately corresponds to the proportional limit of the composites. Because the moving average begins to reduce after the AE signal of 5 V. The highest proportional limit was observed in the 3.7 mol. % composite compared to the other composites as expected by FEA.

Although the origin of small AE signals below 5 V is not detected by optical microscope observation, the AE signals should be caused by interfacial debonding which is enhanced by tensile strain of the composite as estimated by FEA. The interfacial debonding due to tensile residual stress at fiber/ matrix interface was reported in the SiC_f/LAS composite [13]. Surgeon et al. reported that small AE signals corresponded to interfacial debonding or delamination in the 2D- 45/45° SiC_f/BMAS composite[14].

Fig. 6 Optical microscope images of tensile- surface of the flexural specimen relaxed from 0, 2.5, 0.5 % strain.
 (a) SiC_f/SiO₂- 3.7 mol.% Al₂O₃, (b) SiC_f/SiO₂- 30 mol.% Al₂O₃, (c) SiC_f/SiO₂- 50 mol.% Al₂O₃

If the elastic limit corresponds to the initial AE signal, strain levels at the AE signal are 0.101% for 3.7 mol. % composite, 0.125% for 30 mol. % composite, 0.112% for 50 mol. % composite. There is no relationship between thermal residual stress developed in the matrix and the elastic limit. On the other hand, if the elastic limit equals to the proportional limit (approximately initial AE signal above 5 V), strain levels of the composites at the AE signal are 0.525% for 3.7 mol. % composite, 0.345% for 30 mol. % composite, 0.168% for 50 mol. % composite. It is clear that the proportional limit depends on the thermal residual stress.

According to the BHE theory [2], critical matrix cracking stress “ σ_o ” is expressed as follows.

$$\frac{\sigma_o}{E_c} (= \varepsilon_m) = \frac{\sigma^*}{E_c} - \frac{P}{E_m}, \quad \frac{\sigma^*}{E_c} = \left[\frac{6V_f^2 E_f \tau_i \gamma_m}{V_m E_c E_m^2 r_f} \right]^{1/3}$$

where $\sigma, \varepsilon, E, V, r, \tau, \gamma$ indicate stress, strain, elastic modulus, fiber volume fraction, fiber radius, interfacial shear stress, surface energy, respectively. Subscripts c, f, m, i indicate composite, fiber, matrix, interface, respectively. And P indicates residual stress developed in the matrix parallel to the fiber axis. Elastic moduli listed in Table 1 are used for this calculation. The values of fiber volume fraction and interfacial shear stress τ_i in the composites are obtained experimentally in this work. The surface energy of the matrix γ_m is assumed to equal to that of mullite, 2.2 (J/ m²) [15]. Thermal residual stress P was given by FEA. As the result, calculated matrix cracking strain $\varepsilon_m = (\sigma^*/E_c - P/E_m)$ was 0.549 (0.257 + 0.292) % for 3.7 mol. % composite, 0.150 (0.121 + 0.029) % for 30 mol. % composite, 0.032 (0.090 - 0.058) % for 50 mol. % composite, respectively. In the 30 and 50 mol. % composite, fine matrix crackings were observed at low strain levels as shown in Fig. 6. On the contrary, in the 3.7 mol. % composite,

the first matrix crack was not found until the composite fracture. In BHE theory, the process of multiplex fine crack growth are not accounted and only instantaneous planar crack formation in the matrix is assumed. This will be a reason of the error in the case of the 30 and 50 mol. % composite. As to the 3.7 mol. % composite, good agreement is found with the BHE model. The fracture behavior of the 3.7 mol. % composite will satisfy the presupposition of the BHE model.

Comparison of the flexural fracture behavior at 298 K and 1573 K

Load-displacement curves during the flexural test at 298 K and 1573 K are shown in Fig.7. In the 3.7 mol. % composite, over 90 vol.% of matrix is composed with SiO₂ glass, which leads to plastic deformation at 1573 K. On the other hand, the network structure of the primary mullite crystals in the 30, 50 mol. % composites will improve the high temperature strength of the matrix.

Fig. 7 Load- displacement curves of flexural test of the composites., SEM images show morphologies of the primary mullite crystal in the matrices.

CONCLUSIONS

1. No clear relationship between thermal residual stress and ultimate strength was not found.
2. The highest proportional limit will be caused by the highest compressive residual stress in the matrix of SiO₂- 3.7 mol. % Al₂O₃ composite. However, no apparent matrix cracking stress was detected by monitoring AE signals during three-point flexural test.
3. The highest fracture strain is observed in the 50 mol. % composite with the highest compressive residual stress in the fiber compared to the other composites.
4. The network structure that the primary mullite crystal bonds each other in the SiO₂- 30, 50 mol. % Al₂O₃ matrix composite will be effective to improve high temperature strength.

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